

CMS scheduling problem considering material handling and routing flexibility

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Abstract

Cell manufacturing as an application of group technology increases the flexibility and efficiency of the production. Cell scheduling problem, one of the subjects in cell manufacturing, has not been widely studied by researchers compared with other problems in cell manufacturing. In spite of great importance of material handling in cell scheduling, it has not been paid enough attention by researches. In this paper, a new mathematical model for cell scheduling problem considering material handling time and routing flexibility is proposed. The proposed model belongs to the mixed-integer nonlinear programs (MINLP). A linearization procedure is proposed to convert the MINLP to an integer program (IP) in order to develop more powerful optimization tools. Furthermore, a simulated annealing-based heuristic is developed to solve the large-size problems.

Keywords: Cell manufacturing, Routing flexibility, Material handling, Simulated annealing.